

Evaluating the Informed Health Choices learning resources secondary school intervention in Kenya

INTRODUCTION

CHOICE project is a research collaboration that seeks to improve health literacy by developing and testing resources that can be used to enable young people to make informed personal choices about their health (health choices learning-resources) and to participate as scientifically literate citizens in informed debate about health policies (health policy learning-resources).

In Kenya, the study is being conducted by researchers from the Tropical Institute of Community Health and Development and will involve continuous interaction with students, teachers, development partners, policymakers, and researchers. The information in this document is meant to help you decide whether or not to take part in this study but first, there are a few things to note.

- You are being asked to allow your participation in this research because you are a potential participant and an adult of legal consenting age.
- We anticipate that once you agree to participate you will be in the study for a period of one school term (first term 2022), with follow-up after one year.
- You will be offered a copy of this form for your future reference.
- Please feel free to ask if you have any questions or concerns at any time before the start or during the conduct of the research.

1. WHY IS THIS RESEARCH BEING CONDUCTED?

This collaborative research project aims to improve population health outcomes by improving health literacy in low-income countries. We will do this by developing and evaluating two strategies for improving health literacy: resources that can be used to enable young people to make informed personal choices about their health (health choices learning-resources) and to participate as scientifically literate citizens in informed debate about health policies (health policy learning-resources).

2. HOW WILL THE STUDY BE CONDUCTED AND YOUR INVOLVEMENT?

The study will be conducted in over 80 schools in Kenya, during the school term. All the selected schools will be allocated to either of the study arms using computer-generated randomization. Schools in the intervention arm together with their teachers will learn resources developed and

continue learning the normal curriculum. In the control arm, students will continue with the curriculum as normal during the school term.

The Critical Thinking about Treatment Test will be given to each student and teacher at the end of the term to assess whether he/she was able to apply knowledge gained from the learning resources. We will administer the questionnaires again after one year to find out if the children retained what they learned.

We will provide the resources and training to schools allocated to the control arm after the one-year follow-up assessment. In addition to the data from the test results, we will ask your school to provide us with data on students' class performance on the ministry of education curriculum (end terms scores) as well as their class attendance data for the period of the trial. We will interview some teachers, education officers, students from schools in the intervention arm regarding the process of using resources.

3. POSSIBLE RISKS TO YOU

We anticipate that your school participation in the study/research presents no risk to you as an individual. However, participation in this study might in some way interfere with your work if you are required to participate in study activities during work hours.

4. POSSIBLE BENEFITS TO YOU

Your participation in the study will equip you with skills to enable you to obtain, process, and understand health information that you need to make appropriate healthcare decisions. You will benefit from free health information.

5. COST TO THE PARTICIPANT

You will incur no cost whatsoever other than time as a result of taking part in the study.

6. COMPENSATION

You will not gain any form of compensation, monetary or otherwise for participating in the study but appropriate daily expenses in form of lunch and transport will be reimbursed if you attend any study-related meetings or workshops.

7. CONFIDENTIALITY

The information you give during the conduct of this research will be kept confidential by the ethical standards agreed upon by the local and international organizations governing the conduct of

research involving human participants. Any information resulting from this study, if published in scientific journals or presented at scientific meetings, will not reveal your identity.

8. RIGHT TO REFUSE/WITHDRAW

Your participation in this research is purely voluntary and you are free to decline to take part or withdraw at any time without any repercussions.

9. QUESTIONS ABOUT THE RESEARCH

In case of any further questions, please contact Prof. Margaret Kaseje, the Principal Investigator in Kenya working at Tropical Institute of Community Health and Development (TICH): Tel: 0715021955 or Ms. Faith Chesire on 0721576525.

10. DECLARATION OF CONSENT

The information about this study has been availed and explained to me and all my questions have been answered. I have read this form and I feel that I have had enough information and time to consider my decision to join the study. I fully understand that by signing this form, I do not waive any of my legal rights, nor does it relieve the study investigators their duty (liability), but merely indicates that I have been informed about the research study in which I am voluntarily agreeing to take part. A copy of this form will be availed to me. Having understood all the information pertaining to this study I, therefore, agree to my participation in this study by appending my signature and name below.

Research Participant

Name:

Signature:

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Date:

Tel number:

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Study Participant consent to use your video and/or photo in the project

Your signature: _____ Date _____